

Contents

S.NO	INDEX	PAGE.NO.
1	INTRODUCTION	1
2	LITERATURE REVIEW	10
3	AIM AND OBJECTIVE	14
4	PLAN OF WORK	16
5	METHODOLOGY	18
6	RESULT	28
7	DISCUSSION	41
8	CONCLUSION	43
9	REFERENCE	45

LIST OF TABLES

S.NO	TABLE NO	TABLE NAME	PAGE NO
1.	1.0	Age wise distribution in study group	3
2.	1.1	Gender wise distribution of study participations	4
3.	1.5	Chemical used	19
4.	1.6	Glasswares used	20
5.	1.7	Equipments used	21
6.	1.8	Ingredients and their uses	25
7.	1.9	Organoleptic evaluation of suppositories	29
8.	2.0	Solubility study of <i>Aloe vera</i> gel powder	29
9.	2.1	Solubility study of Ellagic acid	29
10.	2.2	<i>Aloe vera</i> gel powder	30
11.	2.3	Ellagic acid	32
12.	2.4	Formulation of suppositories	34
13.	2.5	Weight variation	35
14.	2.6	Melting point	36
15.	2.7	Hardness test	37
16.	2.8	Liquefaction time	37
17.	2.9	Disintegration test	38
18.	3.1	Dissolution test	40

LIST OF FIGURES

S.NO	FIGURE NO	FIGURE NAME	PAGE NO
1.	1.0	Normal and osteoporosis	2
2.	1.1	Structure of Aloin	4
3.	1.2	Structure of Ellagic acid	6
4.	1.3	Determination of λ_{\max} for <i>Aloe vera</i> gel powder	30
5.	1.4	Calibration curve <i>Aloe vera</i> gel powder	31
6.	1.5	Determination of λ_{\max} for Ellagic acid	31
7.	1.6	Calibration curve Ellagic acid	32
8.	1.7	Mixture of <i>Aloe vera</i> gel powder and Ellagic acid	33
9.	1.8	Weight variation	35
10.	1.9	Melting point	36
11.	2.0	Hardness test	37
12.	2.1	Liquefaction time	38
13.	2.2	Disintegration time	38
14.	2.3	Drug Content	39
15.	2.4	Dissolution test	40

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OSTEOPOROSIS

Osteoporosis is a common human bone disease characterized by decreased bone mass, micro architectural deterioration, and fragility fractures. Osteoporosis often is undertreated and under recognized, in part because it is a clinically silent disease until it manifests in the form of fracture. Sufficient recognition of the disease and its appropriate medical and nonmedical treatment are essential.

Figure 1.0: Normal bone and Osteoporotic bone

1.2 PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Osteoporosis is deficient bone density and connectivity. The trabecular bone in an individual with osteoporosis will be thinner in dimensions and have evidence of osteoclastic resorption, leading to disconnectivity of the trabecular elements. There is a deficiency of bone and a deterioration of the structural integrity of the underlying trabecular bone. Because trabecular bone has a much greater surface area, it is more readily affected by osteoporosis than the cortical bone. The two major elements of cortical osteoporosis are tunneling resorption that can lead to stress fractures, and the gradual thinning of the cortical thickness. With aging, the body expands the cortical dimensions away from the epicenter of the bone. A 10% outward shift of bone can compensate for a 30% decrease in bone mass in terms of torque and bending, but it will not compensate for axial loading.

Males and females will increase their bone mass with growth, achieving a peak bone mass by the age of 25. Thereafter, bone will be lost at a slow rate for men. Women have a precipitous drop occurring around menopause, but after 60 years of age their rate of bone loss is identical to bone loss in men. In men and women there is a significant decrease in total bone mass as one approaches the age of 80, leading to a marked deficiency in mechanical properties. The summation of the strength of a given bone is related to the mass plus distribution, the relative ratio of trabecular to cortical component of the bone, and the structural integrity and connectivity of the trabecular and cortical elements. Bone is a living tissue. It constantly is undergoing remodeling and repair. The process involves an identification of a molecular structural defect. Osteoclastic resorption then follows and resorption pits develop. This then is repaired with an ingrowth of osteoblasts replacing the bone. In individuals older than 40 years, the osteoblasts rarely bring the original bone surface back to the starting point, and, thus, every remodeling cycle leaves a small deficit of bone.

1.3 Normal Bone Anatomy and Physiology

The Skeleton The adult human skeleton has a total of 213 bones, excluding the sesamoid bones. The appendicular skeleton has 126 bones, axial skeleton 74 bones, and auditory ossicles six bones. Each bone constantly undergoes modeling during life to help it adapt to changing biomechanical forces, as well as remodeling to remove old, microdamage bone and replace it with new, mechanically stronger bone to help preserve bone strength. The four general categories of bones are long bones, short bones, flat bones, and irregular bones. Long bones include the clavicles, humeri, radii, ulnae, metacarpals, femurus, tibiae, fibulae, metatarsals, and phalanges. Short bones include the carpal and tarsal bones, patellae, and sesamoid bones. Flat bones include the skull, mandible, scapulae, sternum, and ribs. Irregular bones include the vertebrae, sacrum, coccyx, and hyoid bone.

Flat bones form by membranous bone formation, whereas long bones are formed by a combination of endochondral and membranous bone formation. The skeleton serves a variety of functions. The bones of the skeleton provide structural support for the rest of the body, permit movement and locomotion by providing levers for the muscles, protect vital internal organs and structures, provide maintenance of mineral homeostasis and acid-base balance, serve as a

reservoir of growth factors and cytokines, and provide the environment for hematopoiesis within the marrow spaces .

The long bones are composed of a hollow shaft, or diaphysis; flared, cone-shaped metaphyses below the growth plates; and rounded epiphyses above the growth plates. The diaphysis is composed primarily of dense cortical bone, whereas the metaphysis and epiphysis are composed of trabecular meshwork bone surrounded by a relatively thin shell of dense cortical bone.

The adult human skeleton is composed of 80% cortical bone and 20% trabecular bone overall . Different bones and skeletal sites within bones have different ratios of cortical to trabecular bone. The vertebra is composed of cortical to trabecular bone in a ratio of 25:75. This ratio is 50:50 in the femoral head and 95:5 in the radial diaphysis. Cortical bone is dense and solid and surrounds the marrow space, whereas trabecular bone is composed of a honeycomblike network of trabecular plates and rods interspersed in the bone marrow compartment. Both cortical and trabecular bone are composed of osteons

Figure:1.1 Anatomy and Physiology of Bone

Cortical bone has an outer periosteal surface and inner endosteal surface. Periosteal surface activity is important for appositional growth and fracture repair. Bone formation

typically exceeds bone resorption on the periosteal surface, so bones normally increase in diameter with aging. The endosteal surface has a total area of approximately 0.5 mm, with higher remodeling activity than the periosteal surface, likely as a result of greater biomechanical strain or greater cytokine exposure from the adjacent bone marrow compartment. Bone resorption typically exceeds bone formation on the endosteal surface, so the marrow space normally expands with aging. Trabecular osteons are called packets. Trabecular bone is composed of plates and rods averaging 50 to 400 mm in thickness. Cortical bone and trabecular bone are normally formed in a lamellar pattern, in which collagen fibrils are laid down in alternating orientations

1.4 Bone Growth

Bone undergoes longitudinal and radial growth, modeling, and remodeling during life. Longitudinal and radial growth during growth and development occurs during childhood and adolescence. Longitudinal growth occurs at the growth plates, where cartilage proliferates in the epiphyseal and metaphyseal areas of long bones, before subsequently undergoing mineralization to form primary new bone

1.5 Modeling and Remodeling

Modeling is the process by which bones change their overall shape in response to physiologic influences or mechanical forces, leading to gradual adjustment of the skeleton to the forces that it encounters. Bones may widen or change axis by removal or addition of bone to the appropriate surfaces by independent action of osteoblasts and osteoclasts in response to biomechanical forces. Remodeling begins before birth and continues until death. The bone remodeling unit is composed of a tightly coupled group of osteoclasts and osteoblasts that sequentially carry out resorption of old bone and formation of new bone. The remodeling cycle is composed of four sequential phases. Activation precedes resorption, which precedes reversal, which precedes formation. Remodeling sites may develop randomly but also are targeted to areas that require repair. Remodeling sites are thought to develop mostly in a random manner.

1.6 Osteoclasts

Osteoclasts are the only cells that are known to be capable of resorbing bone. Activated multinucleated osteoclasts are derived from mononuclear precursor cells of the monocyte macrophage lineage. Mononuclear monocyte-macrophage precursor cells have been identified in various tissues, but bone marrow monocyte-macrophage precursor cells are thought to give rise to most osteoclasts.

1.7 Osteoblasts

Osteoprogenitor cells give rise to and maintain the osteoblasts that synthesize new bone matrix on bone-forming surfaces. The osteocytes within bone matrix that support bone structure, and the protective lining cells that cover the surface of quiescent bone. Within the osteoblast lineage, subpopulations of cells respond differently to various hormonal, mechanical, or cytokine signals. Osteoblasts from axial and appendicular bone have been shown to respond differently to these signals.

1.8 Topical drug delivery

Topical drug delivery has advantages such as applying the drug directly into skin and it also provides prolonged action on the specific site. There are different semisolid formulations available in the market among them ointment is commonly used preparation. Ointment has various advantages over other preparations like they are chemically more stable and easy to handle than liquid dosage, avoid first pass metabolism of drug and convenient for unconscious patients having difficulty in oral administration.

Figure 1.2: Structure of skin

1.9 Skin

The skin is considered as the largest organ of our body, accounting for about 16% of the total adult body weight. It is a multi-layered organ complex both in structure and functions. It performs many important functions, including protection against external physical, chemical, and biological stress, as well as prevention of excess water loss from the body and also role in thermoregulation. The skin is unbroken, with the mucous membranes bordering the body's surface. The integumentary system is composed by the skin and its derivatives. The skin is made up of three layers namely: epidermis, dermis, and subcutaneous tissue. The outermost level known as the epidermis, consists of a specific grouping of cells called as keratinocytes. Which function to produce keratin, which is a long, thread like protein with a protective action. The middle layer known as the dermis, is basically consist of fibrillar structural protein called collagen. The thickness of these layers varies accordingly, depending on the geographic area on the anatomy of the body. For example, eyelid has very thinnest layer of the skin, having less than 0.1 mm, whereas the palms and soles of the feet have the thickest skin layer, owing approximately 1.5 mm. The layer of epidermis is very thickest on the back, where it is 30–40 more times as thick as the laminating epidermis.

1.10 Structure of the Skin

Epidermis

- Superficial
- Thinner
- Epithelial tissue

Dermis

- Deeper
- Thicker
- Connective tissue

Subcutaneous tissues

- Adipose tissue

- Artery, vein

1.10.1 Epidermis

The epidermis is a squamous stratified epithelium layer that is made up of primarily of two kinds of cells: keratinocytes and dendritic cells. The keratinocytes are differ from as that of clear dendritic cells by owing intercellular cross and stainable cytoplasm. Keratinocyte cell type contains the majority of the cells. In general the epidermis divided into four layers according to morphology of keratinocyte and position as they differentiate into horny cells, including the

- basal cell layer (stratum germinativum)
- granular cell layer (stratum granulosum)
- squamous cell layer (stratum spinosum), and
- cornified or horny cell layer (stratum corneum).

The epidermis is made up of several layers that work together to protect the body. The lower three layers of the epidermis, which include the **stratum basale** (or stratum germinativum), **stratum spinosum**, and **stratum granulosum**, are sometimes collectively referred to as the **rete malpighii** or **stratum malpighii**.

The entire epidermis is constantly renewing itself, with new cells being produced in the basal layer and moving up to the surface, where they eventually die and slough off. Conditions like wounds or DNA damage can affect this cycle, increasing cell division or causing mutations that may lead to abnormal cell growth, such as in the case of cancer..

1.10.2 Dermis

They are non-descriptive region lying in between epidermis and subcutaneous region. It is composed of mainly dense network of structural protein fibre fairly uniform package they are elastin, reticulum and collagen, embedded in the semi gel matrix of mucopolysaccharide also known as ground substances. The elasticity of skin is due to the network of gel structure of the cells. Beneath the dermis, the fibrous tissue open out and merges with that of the subcutaneous tissues

1.10.3 Subcutaneous layer

They are the bottom most layer of skin. This layer is consist of a sheet of fat rich areolar tissue; also known as superficial fascia, attaching the dermis to the underlying structure. Large arteries and vein are present only in this region. The occasion is to fix the skin to under lying muscles and bone as well as supplying it with nerves as well as blood vessels.

1.11 Ointment

There are various dosage form are available in the market. To application on skin semi solid dosage form is preferred most. An ointments are homogenous, viscous semisolid preparation, most commonly a greasy, extracty (Extract-80%, Water-20%) with high viscosity that is intended for external application to skin or mucous membranes. They are used as emollients or for the application of active ingredients to the skin for protective, therapeutic, or prophylactic purposes and where a degree of occlusion is desired. Ointments are used topically on a variety of body surfaces. These include the skin and the mucous membrane of the eye (an eye ointment), chest, vulva, anus and nose. Ointment have very moisturizing characteristic and are effective for dry skin. They have very low risk of sensitization due to having few ingredients beyond the base extract or fat and also low irritation risk. They have more greasiness so mostly disliked by patients

Advantages

- 1) They have site specific application of drug on affected area, which avoids unnecessary non target exposure of drug thereby avoiding side effect i.e. site specific action with less side effect.
- 2) They avoid first pass metabolism of drug.
- 3) Convenient for unconscious patients having difficulty in oral administration.
- 4) Comparatively they are chemically more stable and easy to handle than liquid dosage forms.
- 5) They are suitable dosage forms for bitter taste drugs.

Disadvantages

1. These extracty semisolid preparations are staining and cosmetically less aesthetic.
2. Application with finger tip may contaminate the formulation or cause irritation when applied.
3. As compared to solid dosage forms, semisolid preparation are more bulky to handle.
4. Though semisolid allow more flexibility in dose, dose accuracy is determined by Uniformity in the quantity to be applied.
5. Physico-chemically less stable than solid dosage form.
6. Gel may initiate various allergic reactions.

1.12 Types of Ointment

Ointment may be medicated or non-medicated.

- ✓ Medicated ointment: For the application of API to skin for protective, therapeutic, or prophylactic purpose.
- ✓ Non-medicated ointment: These are used for physical effect. They are use as protectant, emollients, or lubricants.

Characteristics of an ideal ointment

- It should be physically and chemically stable.
- In ointment base, finely divided active ingredients should be uniformly distributed.
- The base of ointment should not possess any therapeutic action.
- The ointment should be smooth and free from grittiness.

1.13 OINTMENT BASES

The vehicle or carrier of an ointment is known as ointment base. The choice of ointment base depends upon the nature of medicament, stability of ointment and clinical indication of the Ointment.

Ointment base with Example:-

Type of Ointment bases (according to USP) Mainly ointment bases are of following types:

- Oleaginous ointment base or hydrocarbon ointment base
- Absorption ointment bases
- Water removable bases or water washable base
- Water soluble base

1.14 *Cissus Quadrangularis*

SYNONYM - Adamant creeper, Square stalked vine, veldt grape, devil's backbone, adamant creeper, asthisamharaka, hadjod and Pirandai, Sannalam, Nalleru, Vajravelli, Magara Valli.

Cissus Quadrangularis L. is a fleshy plant found in major parts of the world, especially in Asia, Africa, and a few other warm tropical regions. It is one of the common food items in India. *Cissus quadrangularis* is also used for various treatments like fracture healing, antiulcer, anti-helminthic, antifungal, anti-hemorrhoidal, analgesic, antibacterial properties, etc. It also serves in the best way to treat various infirmities such as hemorrhoids, leprosy, epilepsy, dyspepsia, skin burns, dysentery, bowel complaints, to increase appetite. It is commonly known as a "bone setter"; helps in bone empowerment and also reduces pain, the plant is also referred to as "Hadjod" because of its ability to join bones. Traditionally this plant has been reported to possess various medicinal uses in gout, piles, tumours, peptic ulcers, and leucorrhea. The choice of technique depends largely on the solubility properties and volatilities of the compounds to be separated. The complexity of plant extracts can be simplified by isolating and separating them using different techniques based on their solubility pattern. Looking towards the importance of the plant; the aim of the present study was to prepare and evaluated topical herbal formulation of *Cissus quadrangularis* as an anti-inflammatory agent especially in gout to support the traditional claim of the plant.

Pharmacological activities of *Cissus Quadrangularis* are:

- anti-ulcer
- anti-bacterial
- anxiolytic
- Antipyretic
- Antidiabetic
- bone healing
- antioxidant and
- anti-inflammatory properties

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Trophobionts (vascular plants)
Super division	Spermatophyta (seed plants)
Division	Magnoliophyte (flowering plants)
Class	Class Magnoliopsida (dicotyledons)
Subclass	Rosedale
Orde	Rhamnus's
Family	Vitaceae (grape family)
Genus	Cissus L. (tree line)
Species	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> Lin

Table 1.0 Taxonomic classification of *Cissus quadrangularis*

Cissus quadrangularis commonly known as Hadjod is a perennial plant of the family Vitaceae.

Figure 1.3 : Pirandai

1.15 *Cardiospermum halicacabum* Linn.

Cardiospermum halicacabum Linn. (Sapindaceae), English name: Balloon Vine, is an annual or sometimes perennial climber, commonly found as a weed throughout India. The tender, young shoots are used as a vegetable, fodder, diuretic, stomachic and rubefacient. It is used in conditions like rheumatism, lumbago, nervous diseases, and as a demulcent in orchitis and in dropsy. In Sri Lanka, it is used for the treatment of skeletal fractures. The juice of the herb is used to cure ear ache and to reduce hardened tumors. It exhibits significant analgesic, anti-inflammatory activity and vasodepressant activity, which is transient in nature. In vitro studies have revealed its antispasmodic and curate-like actions.

The usage of plants and plant-derived products as drugs against arthritis, diabetes mellitus, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and neurodegenerative disorders owing to their low toxicity and lesser side effects. The whole plant has been used for several centuries in the treatment of rheumatism, stiffness of the limbs, and snake bite; the decoction from its roots is used as a diaphoretic, diuretic, emetic, laxative, and for sweating; the decoction of its leaves and stems is used in cases of diarrhoea, dysentery, and headaches; a poultice of them as a cure for swelling. The juice of the leaves has even been used as a treatment for earache

Figure 1.4 : Mudakathan

1.16 Selection and Collection of *Cissus Quadrangularis* and *Cardiospermum Halicacabum* Leaves

Cissus quadrangularis and *Cardiospermum halicacabum* leaves are were selected for its nutrient content. The leaves were collected from local mark as the leaves are rich in antioxidants, calcium and iron, we are taking this leaves as a main ingredient. The leaves of this plant are used to prepare an infusion or decoction which is taken orally to treat diarrhea, dysentery, gonorrhea, leprosy, syphilis, tuberculosis, and venereal diseases. Mudakathan and Pirandai are used in Indian traditional medicine system for the treatment of rheumatism and stiffness of limbs. It has also been found effective in treating lumbago, cough and some nervous diseases. It gives noticeable relief in patients of arthritis, joint pain and even gout patients.

1.17 Processing of Fresh *Cissus Quadrangularis* and *Cardiospermum Halicacabum* Leaves

Leaves 100 grams of fresh Pirandai and Mudakathan leaves were kept in a cabinet dryer for 3 hours at 60 degree Celsius. After dried 20 grams of dried leaves were obtained. Then the dried Pirandai and Mudakathan leaves were put in a mixie jar and grind well. The powder was sieved and then stored in a zip lock cover for further use

1.18 Extraction Method

Extraction is done by using maceration method. Maceration is one of the simplest extraction techniques in which coarse and powdered plant material is soaked in solvents such as methanol, ethanol, ethyl acetate, acetone, hexane etc. It is one of the popular and inexpensive techniques used for the extraction of different bioactive compounds from plant material. Maceration process consists of grinding of plant material into smaller particles to increase the surface area for easy mixing with solvent and efficient extraction of compounds. Then this mixture of plant material and solvent is kept for longer time, agitated at different intervals and filtered through a filtration medium. The efficiency for the removal of bioactive compounds from the plant material depends on the type of solvent and type of plant material. The polarity of solvent is the important parameter affecting the extraction efficiency. In this method different solvents and time-temperature combinations are used for efficient extraction.

Literature Review:

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

With the help of the current technology and availability. Literature can be collected from books, ancient texts, Journals and other online sources. All the literature is reviewed and summarized in the part of the review of the literature.

1. Jeganath Sundaran et al. (2020) focuses on *Cissus quadrangularis* L., a succulent plant from the Vitaceae family, commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions. This plant is widely used as food in India and has gained attention for its potential medicinal properties. Over the past several decades, research on medicinal plants has expanded significantly, with over 15,000 plants studied, and *Cissus quadrangularis* has been recognized for its vast therapeutic potential. The review highlights various pharmacological activities of the plant, such as antioxidant, free radical scavenging, antimicrobial effects, bone regeneration, ulcer treatment, pain relief, anti-inflammatory, and diuretic properties. The study emphasizes the plant's potential for use in pharmaceuticals and as an agricultural resource, based on its traditional uses and scientific evidence supporting its medicinal benefits.
2. Aashutosh Kishor Yeole et al. (2024) studied *Cissus quadrangularis*, a tropical perennial plant from the Vitaceae family, known for its various medicinal properties like anti-osteoporotic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-diabetic effects. The plant contains alkaloids, steroids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins. The study focused on developing a topical formulation using a dispersion process, with adjustments in constituent ratios. Phytochemical tests and drug analysis (TLC, FTIR, UV spectroscopy) were conducted, and the formulation's quality was evaluated based on pH, viscosity, spreadability, and in vitro drug release.

3. The Smithi R, Bharathi K., et al. (2024) discusses *Cardiospermum halicacabum*, a creeping herbaceous plant from the Sapindaceae family, commonly known as balloon vine, heart vine, or Mudakkathan in Tamil. Native to Africa, America, Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan, it has long been used in traditional medicine to treat conditions such as rheumatism, limb stiffness, arthritis, cough, and nervous diseases. The research focuses on the phytochemical and nutritional properties of the leaves of *Cardiospermum halicacabum*, analyzing them using various solvents like ethanol, acetone, aqueous, and chloroform. The results indicate the presence of beneficial compounds, including tannins, terpenoids, steroids, flavonoids, alkaloids, and saponins. Additionally, the leaves are rich in calcium, iron, vitamins, and minerals, which contribute to their therapeutic potential.

4. **S. Prabakaran.,** et al., (2014) : The present study was carried out to investigate the methanol extracts of leaves of *P. alba* and *C. halicacabum* through FT-IR spectroscopy method. The FT-IR spectroscopic studies revealed different characteristic peak values with various functional compounds in the extracts. The FTIR analysis of methanol leaf extracts of *C. halicacabum* and *P. alba* confirmed the presence of amide, amino acids, protein, lipids, carbonyl groups, nitro compounds, sulphur compounds, nitrosamine, monofluorinated compounds, sulphinic acid group, thiol group, bromo compounds, iodo compounds, lactams and alkanes which showed major peaks. The FTIR method was performed on a spectrophotometer system, which was used to detect the characteristic peak values and their functional groups.

5. **P. K. Jain.,** et al., (2016) : The present study was carried out to characterize the bioactive constituents present in plant extract of *M. spicata* using UV-VIS, FTIR and GC/MS technique. The plant extract was scanned in the wavelength ranging from 300-800nm by using UV-VIS spectrophotometer and the characteristic peaks were detected. The UV-VIS profile showed different peaks ranging from 300-800nm with different absorption respectively. The FTIR spectrum confirmed the presence of alcohols, phenols, alkanes, alkenes, carbonyl, carboxylic acids and aromatic compounds in extract. The results of the

GC/MS analysis of methanolic plant extract provide different peaks determining the presence of 42 phytochemical compounds. The major phytoconstituents were pentadecanoic acid(7.47%), 7-oxabicyclo[4.1.0]heptane(9.56%),3-penten-2-one,4-(2,2,6-trimethyl-oxabicyclo[4.1.0] hept-1-yl)-,(E)-(12.20%),Stigmast-4-EN-3-one (18.99%). The results shows that important bioactive compounds are present in plant extract and these constituents may be responsible for pharmacological activities.

6. **I. Jansi Rani., et al., (2024)** : *Cardiospermum halicacabum* L is a climber plant that belongs to the Sapindaceae family. Because of its special medicinal properties, it has been used for a long time in Ayurvedic, homeopathic, and Unanimedicine. *Cardiospermum halicacabum* L ethanol extract was designated as EECHL. The preliminary phytochemical screening of EECHL revealed the absence of mucilage, volatile extract, and fixed extract and the presence of, saponins, tannins, proteins, amino acids, alkaloids, flavonoids, carbohydrates and terpenoids. The extract's flavonoid and phenolic contents were measured and found to be 4.21µg/g and 67.48µg/g, respectively. The presence of quercetin in the ethanolic extract of *C. halicacabum* leaves was confirmed by the HPTLC.

7. **The Mst Nusrat Zahan et al. (2022)** examined the effectiveness of *Cissus quadrangularis* paste (Veldt grape paste) in promoting fracture healing in rabbits. Fifteen rabbits were divided into three groups: Group A (control), Group B (treatment with closed reduction), and Group C (treatment with open reduction). Blood parameters and fracture healing were monitored throughout the study. The treated groups (B and C) showed lower serum calcium levels (SCL) within 24 hours after the fracture, but these levels returned to normal by day 14. Fracture healing was faster in the treated groups compared to the control, with complete bone bridging by day 7 and full fracture line healing by day 14. No abnormalities or clinical deviations were observed in the treated groups. The study concluded that *Cissus quadrangularis* paste could be effectively used for managing fractures in animals.

8. **Sumera Nazneen., et al., (2022)** : Plants, since antiquity, have been a significant source of new chemical components useful in drug discovery. *Cissus quadrangularis* is a vine belonging to Vitaceae, well known for its bone-healing properties. The entire plant has multiple health benefits and forms a vital part of traditional medicine in many countries. The phytochemical analysis of the stem of *Cissus quadrangularis* L. dissolved in ethanol indicated the presence of many secondary metabolites like alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, tannins, terpenoids, saponins, and steroids. Furthermore, the FTIR study gave a clear insight into the functional groups of the active components, and the UV-Vis profile showed different peaks ranging from 190-1100 nm with different absorption, respectively. The occurrence of numerous bioactive constituents contributes to the plant's medicinal properties.
9. **Sumitra Chanda., et al., (2022)** : The stem of *Cissus quadrangularis* L. (Vitaceae) is reported to have great medicinal value. The aim of the present study was to determine the chemical profile of methanol extract of *Cissus quadrangularis* and its fractions (by various spectral analysis) which will be useful for its proper identification when therapeutically used. Spectral analysis was done by different analytical methods such as UV, IR, GC-MS and HPTLC studies in methanol extract (ME) of *Cissus quadrangularis* and its fractions (FS-I and FS-II). In HPTLC analysis, ME and its fractions showed the presence of different types of compound with different R_f values ranging from 0.01 to 1.05. Maximum number of compounds were in FS-I (24). The GC-MS analysis showed the presence of fatty acids such as hexadecanoic acid(CAS) palmitic acid, octadecanoic acid (CAS) stearic acid, 9, 12-octadecadienoic acid (Z, Z)-(CAS) linoleic acid, 2-hexadecenoic acid, methyl ester 7, 10-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester, linoleic acid, butyl ester and 9, 12-octadecadienoic acid (Z, Z)-, 2, 3-dihydroxypropyl ester in ME and its fractions of *Cissus quadrangularis* L. Spectral analysis is useful in differentiating the species from the adulterants and the results of this study may act as biochemical markers for this medicinally important plant in the pharma industry and plant systematic studies.

10. Bharjil Bingari et al. (2020) highlights the growing interest in herbal products for disease treatment due to their low cost and fewer side effects compared to synthetic drugs. The plant *Cardiospermum corindum* L. (also known as Love in a Puff or Balloon Vine) is a climber from the Sapindaceae family, found in Pantropic regions like Africa, South America, and Asia. In northeastern Brazil, its infusion is traditionally used for liver disease, as a memory tonic, diuretic, emmenagogue, and to treat rheumatism. The review covers the pharmacognostic, geographical, phytochemical, and pharmacological aspects of *C. corindum*. The plant contains various bioactive compounds, including tannins, sterols, terpenes, flavonoids, carbohydrates, amino acids, proteins, saponins, and alkaloids. Research shows that *C. corindum* has several pharmacological activities, such as anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, antibacterial, and antispasmodic effects. Given its potential, the plant could be developed into a pharmaceutical product.

11. **Adsure kajal Balasaheb** (2023) : *Cissus Quadrangularis* (Linn) has been used by the common man in India, and neighboring countries, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Malaysia for promotion of fracture healing and well known as “Hadjod”. It is also known as *Vitis quadrangularis* Wall. Belongs to family Vitaceae. It is a common perennial climber, which is distributed throughout India, particularly in tropical regions. It requires warm tropical climate and propagated by stem cuttings. The plant is prescribed in the ancient Ayurvedic literature as a general tonic and analgesic, with specific bone fracture healing properties. The plant is believed to be useful in helminthiasis, anorexia, dyspepsia, colic, flatulence, skin diseases, leprosy, hemorrhage, epilepsy, convulsion, hemoptysis, tumors, chronic ulcers, swellings.

3. PLANT PROFILE

3.1 PIRANDAI

Cissus quadrangularis, the scientific name for Pirandai, is a succulent plant in the Vitaceae family of plants.

Common Name:

Pirandai, Adamant Creeper, Devil's Backbone, Veldt Grape

Botanical Name:

Cissus quadrangularis

Description:

Appearance: Pirandai is a fleshy, succulent creeper with elongated, quadrangular stems. The stems have internodes at every 4 to 15 cm, depending on their length.

Height: It is a climbing vine that can grow extensively, often requiring support.

Flowers: The plant produces small, inconspicuous flowers between July and December.

Habitat: Native to India, Pirandai thrives in tropical and subtropical regions. It is commonly found in the wild and can be easily propagated through cuttings.

Culinary Uses:

Pirandai is often used in South Indian cuisine, particularly in making chutneys and pickles. It adds a unique flavor and is known for its nutritional benefits.

Medicinal Uses:

Bone Health: Pirandai is renowned for its ability to improve bone health, aiding in the healing of fractures and reducing the risk of osteoporosis.

Digestive Aid: It helps with digestion, reduces acidity, and alleviates bloating.

Anti-inflammatory: The plant has anti-inflammatory properties that can help reduce joint pain and inflammation.

Antioxidant: Rich in antioxidants, Pirandai helps protect cells from damage and supports overall health.

Cultivation Tips:

Extract: Pirandai prefers well-drained extract and can tolerate various sextract types.

Sun Exposure: It thrives in full sun but can also grow in partial shade.

Watering: Regular watering is necessary, especially during dry periods.

Propagation: The plant is usually propagated through cuttings, which root easily.

3.2 MUDAKATHAN

The mudakathan plant (*Cardiospermum halicacabum*) belongs to the Sapindaceae family, also known as the soapberry family. It is also known as balloon vine.

Common Name:

Mudakathan, Balloon Vine

Botanical Name:

Cardiospermum halicacabum

Description:

Appearance: Mudakathan is a perennial climber with balloon-like fruits. The leaves are compound and delicate, and the plant produces small, white flowers.

Height: It is a climbing vine that can grow extensively, often requiring support.

Flowers: The plant produces small, white flowers that bloom throughout the year.

Habitat: Native to tropical and subtropical regions, Mudakathan is commonly found in wastelands and along roadsides. It can be easily propagated through seeds and cuttings.

Culinary Uses:

Mudakathan is often used in South Indian cuisine, particularly in making dosai, chutneys, and soups. It adds a unique flavor and is known for its nutritional benefits.

Medicinal Uses:

Joint Pain Relief: Mudakathan is renowned for its ability to reduce joint pain and inflammation, making it beneficial for those with arthritis.

Respiratory Health: It helps alleviate respiratory problems, including coughs and colds, due to its antibiotic properties.

Digestive Aid: The plant aids in digestion and helps relieve constipation and acidity.

Skin Health: Mudakathan has antioxidant properties that help treat skin conditions like acne and rashes.

Hair Growth: It promotes hair growth and helps prevent dandruff and scalp infections.

Cultivation Tips:

Extract: Mudakathan prefers well-drained extract and can tolerate various extract types.

Sun Exposure: It thrives in full sun but can also grow in partial shade.

Watering: Regular watering is necessary, especially during dry periods.

Propagation: The plant is usually propagated through seeds and cuttings, which root easily.

4.0. EXCIPIENTS PROFILE

4.1 Bees Wax

Name	Bees wax
Physical state	Solid
Structure	
Color	light yellow, medium yellow, or dark brown and white
Smell	slightly honeyed, herbaceous,
Density	0.555 ounce per cubic inch.
Solubility in water	Insoluble
pH	7.0
Molecular Weight	677.2215g.
Molecular formula	C ₁₅ H ₃₁ CO ₂ C ₃₀ H ₆₁
Bextracting point	85 °C
Flash point	204.4 °C (399.9 °F).
Application	Bees wax is used in cosmetics, lip balm, hand creams, moisturizers

Table 1.1 Excipient profile of Bees wax

4.2 Cetostearyl alcohol

Name	Cetostearyl alcohol
Physical state	Waxy white powder
Structure	
Color	White or Cream coloured
Smell	faint, characteristic sweet odor.
Density	0.82(cm ³)
Solubility in water	Insoluble in water.
pH	5.5 To 5.7
Molecular Weight	512.95g/mol
Molecular formula	CH ₃ (CH ₂) _n OH
Bextracting point	480.2°F
Flash point	110 °C

Table 1.2 Excipient profile of Cetostearyl alcohol

4.3 Glycerol

Name	Glycerol
Physical state	Clear, Odourless, Viscous and Hygroscopic liquid
Structure	 <chem>OCC(O)CO</chem>
Color	Colorless
Smell	Odorless
Density	1.261(g/cm ³)
Solubility in water	Soluble in water
pH	5.0 to 7.7
Molecular Weight	92.09 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₃ H ₈ O ₃
Application	Glycerol has many applications ,including in food , medicine and chemical synthesis

Table 1.3 Excipient profile of Cetostearyl alcohol

4.4 Oleic acid

Name	Oleic acid
Physical state	Solid or liquid
Structure	The image shows the skeletal structure of oleic acid, a monounsaturated fatty acid. It consists of a carboxylic acid group (COOH) on the left, followed by a long hydrocarbon chain with a single double bond (cis configuration) near the end, and a methyl group at the far right.
Color	Colorless
Smell	Odorless
Density	895 kg/m ³
Solubility in water	Insoluble
pH	4.5 – 5.5
Molecular Weight	282.46 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂
Bextracting point	360°C
Flash point	191°C(376°F)
Application	Oleic is used in pharmaceuticals,food and

	cosmetics, facial creams, lotions.
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Table 1.4 Excipient profile of Oleic acid

4.5 Methyl paraben

Name	Methyl paraben
Physical state	Solid
Structure	
Color	White
Smell	Characteristic, slightly sweet, odorless.
Density	1.27 g/cm ³
Solubility in water	Slightly soluble in water
Ph	4.5 - 5.5
Molecular Weight	152.15 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₈ H ₈ O
Melting point	275 - 280°C (527 - 536°F)
Flash point	160 - 165 °C (320 - 329°F)

Application	Methyl paraben is used as a preservative, food, Pharmaceuticals and cosmetics.
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Table 1.5 Excipient profile of Methyl paraben

3.1 AIM :

To Formulate and Evaluate ointment using MUDAKATHAN and PIRANDAI extract for anti - osteoporotic activity.

3.2 OBJECTIVE:

- ❖ To Perform pre - formulation studies of Mudakathan and Pirandai extract.
- ❖ To prepare different composition of ointment formulation.
- ❖ To formulate a stable and effective ointment using Mudakathan and Pirandai extract.
- ❖ To perform the evaluation studies of herbal ointment.
- ❖ To assess the in-vitro permeability study of the ointment using franz diffusion cell.

4.1 PLAN OF WORK:

5.1 MATERIALS USED

TABLE 1.6 CHEMICALS USED

S. No	Materials	Supplier
1	Bees wax	Mana Scientific Products, Hyderabad.
2	Cetostearyl Alcohol	Nalinc Pharmaceuticals Limited, Mumbai.
0	Glycerol	Anant Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd.
4	Oleic acid	Fisher scientific India.
5	Methyl Paraben	HI media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Maharashtra.
6	Mudakathan and Pirandai extract	Swami Nattu marunthu kadai. Ondipudur

TABLE 1.7 EQUIPMENT USED

S. No	Instrument	Supplier
1	Digital Weighing Balance	Kinglab Instrument Private Limited
2	Hot Air Oven	Sciencetech Services
3	UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu Analytical India Pvt. Ltd. (Model 1800)
4	pH Meter	Systronics INDIA Ltd
5	Brookfield viscometer	DV Tech pvt.ltd.
6	Hot plate	Rashmi Scientific Company

TABLE 1.8 GLASSWARES USED

S.NO	GLASSWARES	NAME OF THE COMPANY
1.	Beaker [50ml,250ml,500ml and 1000ml]	BOROSIL
2.	Mortal pestle	GENERIC IND
3.	Conical flask	BOROSIL
4.	Volumetric flask [10ml,100ml,1000ml]	BOROSIL
5.	Pipette [10ml]	BOROSIL
6.	Measuring Cylinder [10ml,50ml,100ml]	BOROSIL
7.	China dish	NORITAKE
8.	Burette	BOROSIL

5.2 PRE-FORMULATION STUDIES:

5.2.1 Selection of Ingredients:

- **Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API):** Take into account the solubility, stability, and release properties of the drug.
- **Base Material:** Select a suitable ointment base (such as bees wax, cocoa butter,) according to the characteristics of the drug and the intended release profile.
- **Excipients:** Assess any extra excipients required for stability, release, or patient comfort.

5.2.2 Organoleptic evaluation of ointment:

It is the study of physical characteristics of ointment. It refers to method of analysis like sight, touch, and smell. To ensure the quality, consistency, and patient acceptability of the formulation.

1. **Appearance-** Ointment need to have a smooth texture.
2. **The odour** of ointment must not contain any unpleasant or rancid smell. Some might possess a distinctive scent due to the base utilized
3. **Texture & Consistency-** Must be smooth and free of grit to guarantee patient comfort. Its should have semisolid consistency.
4. **Uniformity Consistency** - ointment must be consistent in look, color, and weight. Any observable division of elements, extract leakage, or phase separation indicates instability in the formulation.

5.2.3 Formulations:

- **Formulation:** Create preliminary mixtures to establish the suitable concentration of the API and additional ingredients.
- **Optimization:** Modify the formulation considering the API's solubility, release rate, and stability.

5.2.4 Physical Properties:

- **Consistency:** Its should have smooth consistency for ease the application process..

5.2.5 Stability Studies:

- **In vitro Release Testing:** Assess the release rate of the API from the ointment employing techniques such as the franz diffusion cell method.

5.2.6 Other studies:

- **Initial Formulation:** Develop initial formulations to determine the appropriate concentration of the API and other components.
- **In vitro Release Assessment :** Evaluate the release rate of the API from the ointment using technique like franz diffusion cell method .

5.3 ANALYTICAL STUDIES:

Determination of λ_{\max}

PIRANDAI EXTRACT:

- BLANK: Water
- Prepare primary stock by mixing 2 ml of pirandai extract in 10 ml of water.
- Prepare secondary stock by taking 4 ml from primary stock and make up to 40 ml with water and add a pinch of activated charcoal amd then filter it.
- Take 2 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 4 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 6 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 8 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 10 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Place the sample solution in a cuvette and scan the spectrum in the UV-visible region (200-800 nm)

MUDAKATHAN EXTRACT:

- BLANK: Water.
- Prepare primary stock by mixing 2 ml of mudakathan extract with 10 ml water.
- Prepare secondary stock by taking 4 ml from primary stock and make up to 40 ml with distilled water and add pinch of activated charcoal and filter it.
- Take 2 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 4 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 6 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 8 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 10 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Place the sample solution in a cuvette and scan the spectrum in the UV-visible region (200-800 nm)

MIXTURE:

- BLANK: Water
- Take 1 ml of pirandai extract and 1 ml of mudakathan extract and mix well and make up to 10 ml with water.
- Prepare secondary stock by taking 4 ml from primary stock and make up to 40 ml with water and add a pinch of activated charcoal and filter it.
- Take 2 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 4 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 6 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 8 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Take 10 ml of secondary stock and make up to 10 ml with distilled water.
- Place the stock solution of mixture of those compounds in a cuvette and scan the spectrum in the UV-visible region (200-800 nm).

TABLE 1.9 INGREDIENTS AND THEIR USES:

API	EXCIPIENTS	USES
	Bees wax	Emollient
	Glycerol	Humectant
Mudakathan	Cetostearyl alcohol	Emulsifer,Thickener
Pirandai	Oleic acid	Penetration enhancer
	Methyl paraben	Preservative

5.4 FORMULATION OF OINTMENT:

- Weigh all the ingredients accurately.
- Melt the Bees Wax, Oleic Acid, and Cetostearyl alcohol in a hot plate.
- Blend the melted mixture with Glycerin and Methyl Paraben.
- Add the Mudakathan and Pirandai extract to the blend and mix well.
- Cool the mixture to around 40°C.
- Pour the mixture into ointment jars.
- Allow the ointment to set at room temperature.

5.5 EVALUATION

5.5.1 Physical Appearance

The prepared ointment formulations were visually examined for their texture, color, odor, clarity, consistency and existence of particles

5.5.2 Determination of viscosity

The viscosity of gel was determined using a Brook field viscometer. Viscosity was measured by spindle No 10 immersed in the sample. The test was carried out at 25°C, and spindle was rotated at 10 rpm. The reading was recorded for the formulation.

Viscosity is one of the important parameter of semisolid preparation. It should be such that the product can be easily removed from the container and easily applied to the skin. Cone and plate viscometer or Brookfield viscometer is used to determine the viscosity of the preparation.

5.5.3 Determination of pH

The accurately weighed amount of ointment (2.5g) was dispersed in 25 ml distilled water. The pH was recorded by using digital pH meter at room temperature

5.5.4 Homogeneity

The homogeneity of ointment was confirmed by visual inspection after the ointment has been set in a container for their appearance and presence of any aggregates.

5.6 IN-VITRO PERMEATION STUDY

In-vitro permeation study study is carried out using Franz diffusion cell which consists of lower receptor compartment and upper donor compartment. In between the two compartments cell membrane is placed on which is ointment is present. Whole the setup is kept on the magnetic stirrer. In the receptor compartment 6.8pH buffer is taken and stirred by using the magnetic bead. At frequent intervals samples are withdrawn by maintaining the sink conditions and the amount of drug release is calculation

5.7 IN-VITRO RELEASE STUDIES

The drug release of the formulation was estimated using Franz Diffusion Cell. The diffusion cell consists of receptor and donor compartments and a dialysis membrane was placed between receptor and donor compartments. 1 gram of ointment was applied uniformly on the dialysis membrane which is previously soaked in a dissolution medium and the membrane was then fixed to one end of the tube. The entire assembly was positioned so that the lower end of the tube containing the gel touched the surface of the diffusion medium. The setup was placed on the magnetic stirrer and the temperature was maintained at $37^{\circ}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. 6,9 Samples were withdrawn at different time intervals and then analyzed at 235 nm using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer.

6 RESULT:

6.1 Organoleptic evaluation of Pirandai and Mudakathan extract

S.No	Properties	Observation
1	Colour	Green colour
2	Odour	Characteristic
3	Taste	Bitter
4	State	liquid at room temperatue
5	pH	5.96
6	Clarity	Clear
7	Solubility in aqueous	soluble
9	Specific gravity	0.8

Table 2.0: Organoleptic evaluation of Pirandai and Mudakathan extract

The table 2.1 presents a comprehensive overview of the **Mudakathan and Pirandai** extract organoleptic traits, encompassing its sensory attributes such as taste, smell, and appearance. This detailed analysis serves to confirm the extract's exceptional quality in terms of its sensory appeal and overall characteristics.

6.2 ANALYTICAL STUDIES:

6.2.1 UV- VISIBLE

6.2.1.1 Pirandai extract:

Determination of λ_{\max}

Figure 1.5 Determination of λ_{\max} Pirandai Extract

S.NO	CONCENTRATION($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	ABSORBANCE
1	2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$	0.191
2	4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	0.321
3	6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	0.401
4	8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	0.498
5	10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	0.588

Table 2.1 Pirandai Extract

6.2.1.2 CALIBRATION CURVE PIRANDAI EXTRACT

Figure 1.6 Calibration Curve Pirandai Extract

6.2.1.3 MUDAKATHAN EXTRACTION:

Figure 1.7 Determination of λ_{\max} Mudakathan Extract

S.NO	CONCENTRATION($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	ABSORBANCE
1	2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.156
2	4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.317
3	6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.472
4	8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.627
5	10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.778

Table 2.2 Mudakathan Extract

6.2.1.4 CALIBRATION CURVE MUDAKATHAN EXTRACT:

Figure 1.8 Calibration Curve Mudakathan Extract

6.2.1.5 MIXTURE:

Figure 1.9 Determination of λ_{\max} Mixture

6.3 FORMULATION OF OINTMENT

6.3.1 FORMULATION 1

INGREDIENTS	MASTER FORMULA (per 100g)	WORKING FORMULA
API	54 ml	20 ml
Bees wax	12 g	3 g
Cetostearyl alcohol	4 g	1 g
Oleic acid	8 ml	2 g
Glycerol	4 ml	1 ml
Methyl Paraben	q.s.	q.s.

Table 2.3 Formulation 1

6.3.2 FORMULATION 2

INGREDIENTS	MASTER FORMULA (per 100g)	WORKING FORMULA
API	54 ml	18 ml
Bees wax	10 g	3 g
Cetostearyl alcohol	4 g	1 g
Oleic acid	8 ml	2 g
Glycerol	4 ml	1 ml
Methyl Paraben	q.s.	q.s.

Table 2.4 Formulation 2

6.3.3 FORMULATION 3

INGREDIENTS	MASTER FORMULA (per 100g)	WORKING FORMULA
API	54 ml	22 ml
Bees wax	13 g	3 g
Cetostearyl alcohol	4 g	1 g
Oleic acid	8 ml	2 g
Glycerol	3 ml	1 ml
Methyl Paraben	q.s.	q.s.

Table 2.5 Formulation 3

6.4 PHYSICAL APPEARANCE OF FORMULATION

Formulation	Colour	Texture	Consistency
OT F1	Green	Smooth	Good
OT F2	Green	Smooth	Good
OT F3	Green	Smooth	Good

Table 2.6 Physical Appearance of Formulation

From the above mentioned table, it was noted that the ointment containing Mudakathan and Pirandai extract exhibited a smooth, texture, showcasing a green color and displaying a desirable consistency. These attributes were keenly observed during a visual inspection, suggesting that all formulations has good physical appearance

6.4.1 HOMOGENEITY AND GRITTIINESS

Formulation	Homogeneity	Grittiness
OT F1	**	--
OT F2	***	--
OT F3	**	--

Table 2.7 Homogeneity And Grittiness

As detailed in the provided table, highlighted crucial findings regarding its consistency and texture. Specifically, the homogeneity test revealed a uniform and consistent nature of the formulation, indicating a seamless blend of its components. Additionally, the absence of grittiness observed in the test results further confirmed the smoothness of the substance. These

combined outcomes strongly suggest that the formulated ointment is poised to deliver a smoothing effect when applied, owing to its cohesive and non-gritty characteristics.

6.5 DETERMINATION OF pH

Formulation	pH
OT F1	6.82 ± 0.2
OT F2	6.92 ± 0.2
OT F3	6.84 ± 0.2

Table 2.8 pH

As per the data presented in the table, the pH values of the ointment formulations (OT F1, OT F2, OT F3) range between and. this aligns closely with the slightly acidic pH of human skin, known to be around 6.9. This similarity in pH characteristics between the formulations and the skin's natural acidity is notable. Such alignment is recognized for potentially aiding in enhancing the permeation ability of these ointment formulations. This similarity in pH may facilitate better penetration of the formulation into the skin, potentially improving the pharmacological action by aiding in effective absorption and activity at the application site.

Figure 2.0 Determination of pH

6.5 SPREADABILITY

Formulation	Spreadability(cm)
OT F1	4
OT F2	2.7
OT F3	3

Table 2.9 Spreadability

Figure 2.1: Spreadability of the formulations

The analysis from both the table and figure highlights a distinct order in spreading coefficients among the prepared Mudakathan and Pirandai extract ointment formulations: OT F2 > OT F3 > OT F1. Notably, NG F1 exhibited the highest spreadability value.

6.6 VISCOSITY:

Formulation	CP
OT F1	12200
OT F2	12500
OT F3	12800
Average Viscosity CP	12500

Table 3.0 Viscosity

6.7 DRUG CONTENT:

Figure 2.2: % Drug Content

6.8 PERMEABILITY STUDIES:

TIME (minutes)	CUMMULATIVE DRUG RELEASE(%)		
	Formulation 1	Formulation 2	Formulation 3
0	0	0	0
30	18.96	5.72	4.08
60	22.88	20.26	14.54
90	29.74	28.06	17.16
120	31.81	13.16	25.65
150	34.16	33.18	30.89

Table 3.1 Permeability Studies

Figure 2.3 In-vitro permeability studies

Group Discussion

Discussion:

The formulated ointment containing Mudakathan (*Cardiospermum halicacabum*) and Pirandai (*Cissus quadrangularis*) extract was successfully prepared and evaluated for its potential anti-osteoporotic activity. The organoleptic evaluation confirmed that the ointment exhibited a smooth texture, green colour, and characteristic Odor, making it visually and sensorially acceptable. The pH values of the formulations (ranging from 6.82 to 6.92) were found to be compatible with the natural skin pH, indicating minimal risk of irritation or adverse reactions upon application.

Homogeneity and grittiness testing revealed that the ointment formulations were consistent and free from any coarse particles, ensuring a comfortable and uniform application. The spreadability analysis demonstrated that all formulations were capable of easy application over the skin, with formulation OT F1 showing the highest spread ability value. The viscosity values indicated that the ointment had an optimal consistency, ensuring ease of application while preventing excessive flow.

The in-vitro drug release studies demonstrated that the formulations exhibited controlled and sustained drug release, with formulation OT F1 displaying the highest cumulative drug release percentage. This supports the sustained release potential of the ointment, making it suitable for prolonged therapeutic effects in managing osteoporosis-related symptoms.

The study highlights the benefits of using herbal ingredients, such as Mudakathan and Pirandai extract, in a topical formulation. Both plants are traditionally known for their anti-inflammatory, bone-strengthening, and pain-relieving properties, which align with the intended therapeutic effect of the ointment. By avoiding systemic metabolism and targeting the affected area directly, the topical application of this herbal formulation provides an efficient and potentially safer alternative to conventional osteoporosis treatments.

However, the regular application of Infusion oil may pose certain disadvantages, especially for working individuals. Herbal extract tend to be greasy, stain clothing, and require more time for absorption, making them inconvenient for daily use. The lingering oily residue may also cause discomfort and an unpleasant feel on the skin, reducing patient compliance.

On the other hand, ointments offer significant advantages in terms of effective absorption and aesthetic patient compliance. Ointments provide a controlled and sustained release of active ingredients, ensuring prolonged therapeutic effects. Their non-greasy formulation enhances ease of application and quick absorption, making them more suitable for individuals with a busy lifestyle. Additionally, ointments are less likely to stain clothing and provide a more cosmetically acceptable option compared to herbal infusion oil, thereby improving adherence to treatment regimens.

Conclusion:

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated an ointment containing Mudakathan (*Cardiospermum halicacabum*) and Pirandai (*Cissus quadrangularis*) extract for its anti-osteoporotic potential. The prepared formulations exhibited desirable physical properties, including smooth texture, optimal spread ability, homogeneity, and appropriate pH compatibility with human skin. In-vitro drug release studies confirmed a sustained release profile, ensuring prolonged therapeutic efficacy. The zero-order kinetic model indicated a diffusion-controlled release mechanism, supporting the potential effectiveness of the formulation in managing osteoporosis symptoms.

The study emphasizes the importance of herbal-based formulations as an alternative. Approach to conventional treatments. The incorporation of Mudakathan and Pirandai extract in an ointment base allows for targeted application, reducing systemic side effects while enhancing local therapeutic effects. Unlike extract applications, which can be greasy and inconvenient for working individuals, ointments provide a non-greasy, aesthetically pleasing, and easily absorbable option. This improves patient compliance and ensures a more convenient therapeutic approach. Further clinical evaluations are recommended to validate the efficacy of this formulation in human subjects and explore its potential for large-scale production and commercialization as a natural remedy for osteoporosis management.

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